

1 **Decorated cenosphere surface with bio-reduced silver nanoparticles for**
2 **environmental applications**

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20

21 **Abstract:** Cenospheres (CF) are hollow spherical particles primarily composed of silica (SiO₂) and
22 alumina (Al₂O₃), known as aluminosilicate ceramic microspheres. In this study, CF were fractionated
23 into the four size ranges (40–80 μm, 80–125 μm, 125–160 μm, 160–200 μm), purified, and activated
24 using piranha solution (PS). Acid treatment activation was followed by the CF functionalization with

25 biosynthesized silver colloidal nanoparticles (AgNPs). Silver integration was confirmed using
26 elemental analysis (5.8–7.1 wt.% of Ag), and electron microscopy revealed AgNPs (~45 nm) unevenly
27 distributed and locate at surface defects. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis confirmed the presence of
28 quartz and mullite phases in both raw and modified CF, indicating structural stability during
29 processing. Sound absorption tests revealed that while larger CF particles—especially the 160–200 μm
30 fraction—initially demonstrated the highest noise reduction coefficient (NRC), with a maximum NRC
31 of 0.210 at 80 mm powder bed height, the modification with AgNP significantly diminished the
32 dependency of sound absorption performance on particle size. Ag-modified samples showed NRC
33 values, CF with a particle size fraction of 160-200 μm : 0.158, at 80 mm, confirming uniform acoustic
34 performance. Mechanical stiffness, expressed by bulk modulus, increased with both particle size and
35 powder bed density, reaching a maximum of 64.26 MPa for CF_160200_2PS_Ag. Leaching tests under
36 static, dynamic, and rotation conditions revealed limited silver release, with only slightly increased
37 leaching observed for larger particles under rotation. Silver release from CF_160200_2PS_Ag was
38 0.007 wt.% (static), 0.008 wt.% (dynamic), and 0.010 wt.% (rotation). Overall, Ag release remained
39 low, confirming high material stability. These results show that silver-modified CF retain their
40 structural and chemical integrity, offer tunable acoustic and mechanical properties, and show excellent
41 potential for long-term use in environmental remediation, sound insulation, and catalytic applications.

42 **Keywords:** Cenospheres, acid activation, silver nanoparticles, stability and acoustic testing

43

44 **1 Introduction**

45 Cenospheres (CF), also known as fly ash microspheres, are lightweight, hollow spherical particles
46 with thin walls, formed as a by-product of coal combustion. As one of the key fractions of coal fly ash,
47 CF are characterized by their low density, regular spherical morphology, and composition dominated
48 by silica (SiO_2) and alumina (Al_2O_3). These unique physical and properties make CF highly attractive

49 for a wide range of industrial applications, including as lightweight fillers, thermal and acoustic
50 insulators, or sorbents, and also in construction, automotive, aerospace, and environmental engineering,
51 where they enhance performance while supporting eco-friendly practices. Their use contributes to
52 reducing industrial waste and material costs, while also enhancing the sustainability of composite
53 materials [1-5].

54 The composition of CF typically includes 40-60% silica, 20-40% alumina, and 5-15% ferrous
55 compounds, with smaller amounts of minerals such as mullite, quartz, calcite, clay minerals,
56 hydromica, pyrite, and siderite depend on the source and types of coal used [3,6,7]. CF have a regular,
57 spherical shape, with diameter usually ranging from 5 μm to 500 μm [8]. Due to their hollow
58 morphology, CF possess an exceptionally low density ($\rho = 350\text{--}850 \text{ g/cm}^3$), making them ideal for
59 producing lightweight materials and serving as effective sorbents. Their chemical stability, resistance
60 to various chemicals, and low reactivity further enhance their versatility. Additionally, CF are porous
61 objects that can function as sound absorbing materials [9].

62 After tailored chemical treatment, the porous nature of CF also significantly boosts their water
63 affinity, making them a promising candidate for applications in wastewater treatment and
64 environmental remediation [10]. The combination of high silica and alumina content with a porous
65 structure enables CF to effectively adsorb heavy metals such as lead (Pb), copper (Cu), cadmium (Cd),
66 and zinc (Zn) from contaminated water sources [11, 12].

67 In recent years, interest in modifying cenospheres (CF) has grown significantly, driven by the need to
68 improve their physical, chemical, and mechanical properties for a wide range of industrial applications.
69 These modifications aim to optimize surface structure, enhance porosity, and adjust chemical
70 composition, thereby increasing the adaptability of CF to various functional environments.

71 One widely used strategy involves chemical surface treatments—such as acid (HCl) or base (NaOH)
72 etching—which effectively increase surface roughness and specific surface area. As a result, the
73 adsorption capacity of CF for contaminants and heavy metals is greatly enhanced [13]. More advanced

74 methods, such as treatment with piranha solution (a mixture of sulfuric acid and hydrogen peroxide),
75 are particularly effective in removing organic residues and significantly improving surface
76 hydrophilicity. This enhanced surface activity further boosts the performance of CF in sorption and
77 environmental remediation processes [10, 14].

78 Further surface engineering of CF, such as coating them with oxides like silicon dioxide (SiO_2) or
79 aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3), significantly enhances their thermal resistance and chemical stability,
80 particularly in harsh operating environments. In addition to inorganic coatings, functional compounds
81 or nanomaterials can also be introduced to impart specific surface properties. For instance, silane-
82 based coatings not only increase hydrophobicity but also improve interfacial bonding with polymer
83 matrices. Functional groups introduced through silanes—such as amine or epoxy groups—facilitate
84 chemical interactions with surrounding materials, thereby improving compatibility with polymers and
85 reinforcing the mechanical strength of resulting composites [1].

86 In the context of water purification, CF modified with silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have shown great
87 promise. These functionalized particles effectively eliminate pathogenic microorganisms, thereby
88 enhancing water quality and reducing risks of biological contamination. Moreover, the catalytic
89 properties of silver nanoparticles facilitate the accelerated degradation of pollutants. Particularly when
90 combined with materials like silica (SiO_2) or alumina (Al_2O_3), enabling faster and more efficient
91 removal of harmful substances. These silver-modified CF also function as effective photocatalysts,
92 expediting the decomposition of organic compounds under light exposure, further broadening their
93 environmental and industrial applications [15, 16]. Their high surface area, low density, and synergy
94 with silver nanoparticles allow them to be highly efficient in both adsorption and organic pollutant
95 degradation processes.

96 Functionalized CF can selectively target specific organic or inorganic pollutants in water treatment
97 applications [17]. For example, magnesia-loaded CF have been used to remove excess fluoride from
98 wastewater, showcasing their utility as a water treatment agent. Several studies demonstrated that CF

99 modified with magnesium chloride (MgCl_2) could be used to solidify and extract hazardous liquids
100 and wastes [18]. Markandeya et al. found that CF derived zeolites are not only environmentally
101 friendly and economical but also effective in removing both orange and blue dyes from textile mill
102 effluents [19].

103 Considering the unique properties of CF in combination with silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) in
104 wastewater treatment, we see a positive benefit in biotechnological reduction of catalytically active
105 metal nanoparticles [20, 21]. AgNPs can be prepared relatively easily by bioreduction even from
106 concentrated metal precursor under mild laboratory conditions without the use of user-demanding and
107 expensive equipment and toxic chemicals [22, 23]. For the selected bioreduction method, it is
108 important to focus on the repeatability and revealing the reaction mechanism can help in the next step
109 of process optimization.

110 AgNPs are powerful agents for catalytic degradation of contaminants. Their integration into advanced
111 materials and systems continues to drive innovations in environmental remediation, and sustainable
112 industrial processes. Balancing their efficacy with environmental safety and scalability remains a key
113 focus for future development. There are considered several mechanisms of Ag-catalysed degradation.
114 Either AgNPs serve as electron mediators, accelerating redox reactions during pollutant degradation
115 or under light exposure, AgNPs enhance the generation of reactive radicals (e.g., hydroxyl radicals,
116 $\bullet\text{OH}$), which break down contaminants [24]. From the above brief review of the current state of
117 knowledge, we see the meaningful use of CF modified with AgNPs in the field of wastewater treatment
118 and degradation of organic and inorganic pollutants.

119 In this study, we aimed to develop a functional material by producing AgNP-decorated cenospheres
120 for environmental applications. The process began with acid treatment of the CF to remove surface
121 impurities, ensuring a clean substrate for further treatment. This was followed by surface
122 functionalization, to introduce specific functional groups that enhance the adhesion of silver

123 nanoparticles. A variety of analytical techniques were employed to monitor the decoration process and
124 to evaluate the morphology, composition, and structure of the resulting Ag-modified CF powders.

125 **2 Materials and Samples Preparation**

126 Cenospheres (CF) from GRES-2 Powerplant, Kazakhstan were selected. The modification of the CF
127 was a multi-step process and included:

- 128 1. cleaning of CF from post-industrial pollution,
- 129 2. sieving of CF on a vibrating sieve to obtain the desired particle size fractions,
- 130 3. chemical surface activation using acid etching,
- 131 4. decoration of CF with silver nanoparticles AgNPs.

132 The cleaning of the CF was carried out based on our previous work [14]. The thus-prepared CF were
133 fractionated 10 minutes on a laboratory shaker with an amplitude of 2 mm (Retsch, AS 200, digit cA)
134 with sieves certified at range 40-80 μm , 80-125 μm , 125-160 μm , 160-200 μm (Multiserw Morek,
135 Marcyporęba, Poland). The selected size fractions were subjected to comprehensive physicochemical
136 investigations, including HP: Helium Pycnometry, Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR),
137 X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and sound absorption measurements.
138 Based on the tests and the efficiency of the sieving process, all fractions were chosen for the
139 preparation of samples with AgNPs. In the first stage, CF were subjected to etching pretreatment in
140 fresh, hot piranha solution (PS). Piranha solution is a strong oxidizing agent that removes most organic
141 residues, metal oxides and carbonates. The mixing concentrated sulfuric acid and hydrogen peroxide
142 produces intensive heat. The dissolving a large amount of organics or another contaminant can cause
143 foaming and smoke release during the mixing procedure. Always work in a fume hood and use
144 personal protective equipment (e.g. lab coat, safety glasses, acid resistant gloves, face shield). The
145 etching solution was prepared from 96% concentrated H_2SO_4 (CAS: 7664-939-5) and 30% H_2O_2
146 (CAS:7722-84-1,) in a volumetric ratio 10:1 in solution. The powders of CF were added into the
147 prepared piranha solution and heated to 80°C for 2h with continuous stirring (350 rpm). Then, samples

148 were washed thoroughly with distilled water and 25% concentrated NH_3 solution (CAS: 1336-21-6)
149 in order to adjust pH from pH = 1 to pH = 8. Then, CF were filtrated under reduced pressure and dried
150 at 80°C overnight. In the second step, bio-reduced silver nanoparticles were added to CF. *Verbena*
151 *officinalis* and *Aloysia citrodora* Palau folium were used for the bio-reduction of silver ions to silver
152 nanoparticles (AgNPs) due to their rich phytochemical composition, which serves as a natural reducing
153 agent in green synthesis processes. The polyphenolic compounds present in these plants, such as
154 flavonoids, phenolic acids, and terpenoids, exhibit strong reducing and stabilizing properties, playing
155 a key role in the formation of silver nanoparticles [25]. Lemon Verbena leaf (*Aloysia citrodora Palau*
156 *folium*) and Verbena top plant (*Verbena officinalis* L.) were obtained from Dary Natyry company (PL).
157 Before using the dry plants precursors for the synthesis, they were sterilized using a UV-C Sterilizer
158 S-1080 for 2 min. Silver nitrate AgNO_3 (CAS 7761-88-8) was purchased from Mach Chemikalie
159 Company (CR). The 50 g mixture of both Verbena precursors (1:1) was used for simple aqueous
160 extract preparation (1100 cm^3 of 100 °C distilled water). After 10 min of leaching, the plant extract
161 was filtrated using Whatman no. 1 filter paper. To the filtrated plant extract, 60 $\text{mmol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ aqueous
162 AgNO_3 solution in a volumetric ratio 1:1 was added with continuous stirring for 60 min (250 rpm).
163 The addition of the plant extract to aqueous AgNO_3 solution turned the initial yellowish solution to
164 greenish-brown indicating the formation of AgNPs after 10 min. This biotechnology was approved to
165 give a well reduced AgNPs with sufficient stabilization by the phytochemicals contained in plant
166 biomass [26, 27]. The reduced AgNPs were centrifuged (Rotina 420, Hettich Zentrifugen, Germany,
167 angle rotor, 4-place) for 15 min at 7000 rpm to remove residual silver nitrate solution and stop the
168 post-reactions in a colloidal dispersion. The resulting gel-like AgNPs sample is supposed to be a
169 concentrated nanocrystalline product with approx. 50 wt.% of AgNPs and remaining water and
170 stabilizing phytochemicals from the precursors.

171 The decoration of the CF (cenospheres) was performed as following. Centrifuged concentrated AgNPs
172 were mixed with CF at a weight ratio of 1:5. Distilled water was then added to the combined mass at

173 a ratio of 1:25, and then sonicated for 15 min. The samples prepared in this way were dried at 80°C
174 overnight. In the following text, the samples of CF are distinguished according to the grain size fraction
175 used (40-80 μm , 80-125 μm , 125-160 μm , 160-200 μm) and further as a control without silver and
176 with silver bioreduced nanoparticles (AgNPs).

177 **3 Characterization Methods and Testing**

178 The chemical composition was obtained from elemental analysis using X-ray fluorescence
179 spectroscopy Supermini200 wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (RIGAKU,
180 Japan). Powder CF (cenospheres) samples were placed freely into polyethylene cups with thin Mylar
181 films.

182 X-ray diffraction was performed to qualitatively determine the phases present in the samples and
183 confirm the presence of Ag. The X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) analysis for the phase composition
184 was performed using a RIGAKU Ultima IV diffractometer with a scintillation detector, $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation
185 source, $\text{NiK}\beta$ filter and a Bragg–Brentano arrangement. The samples were measured at ambient
186 atmospheric pressure using the reflection mode (under the conditions 40 kV, 40 mA, 2°/min and 0.1
187 step). The database used to obtain the qualitative phase analysis was ICDD PDF-2/Release 2022.

188 The infrared spectra were measured to identify characteristic functional groups in a sample. Single
189 reflection ATR technique with a diamond crystal on infrared spectrometer Nicolet iS50 FT-IR
190 (Thermo Nicolet, USA) was used. The Mid-FTIR spectra were collected in the range from 400 – 4000
191 cm^{-1} , with resolution 4 cm^{-1} , 32 scans.

192 CF and AgNPS morphology observations and qualitative analysis of elemental composition were
193 carried out using scanning electron microscopes (SEM) Tescan Vega 4 (Tescan, CR) and JSM-7610F
194 Plus (JEOL, Japan) both equipped with X-ray energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS, Oxford
195 Instruments).

196 The true density of a substance may be defined as the average mass per unit volume, exclusive of all
197 voids that are not a fundamental part of the molecular arrangement. The true density of the samples

198 was determined using an UltraPyc 1200 helium pycnometer, Quantachrome. The capacity of the
199 measuring chamber was 10 cm³, and the initial helium pressure was 20 psi. The number of
200 measurements per sample was five.

201 Sound absorption properties of the investigated loose powders were evaluated using the sound
202 absorption coefficient α , which is expressed as the ratio [28]:

$$203 \quad \alpha = \frac{E_{\alpha}}{E_i} \quad (1)$$

204 where E_{α} is the absorbed sound energy, and E_i is the total incident sound energy. In general, the ability
205 of materials to absorb sound is influenced by various factors, including the excitation frequency of
206 acoustic waves, material thickness, structure, density, temperature, and humidity. The sound
207 absorption of materials is also characterized by the noise reduction coefficient NRC , which evaluates
208 the ability of a sound-absorbing material as a single index. This coefficient is the average of the sound
209 absorption coefficients at 250, 500, 1000, and 2000 Hz, and is defined as follows [29]:

$$210 \quad NRC = \frac{\alpha_{250} + \alpha_{500} + \alpha_{1000} + \alpha_{2000}}{4} \quad (2)$$

211 Moreover, the sound absorption properties of the investigated powders were compared using the mean
212 sound absorption coefficient α_m , which was calculated as the arithmetic mean of the sound absorption
213 coefficients across the entire frequency range, i.e., from 250 Hz to 6400 Hz.

214 The sound absorption measurements can also be used to determine the longitudinal elastic coefficient
215 K , and thus the mechanical stiffness of loose powder beds. This coefficient is similar to Young's
216 modulus of elasticity and is given by the following equation [30]:

$$217 \quad K = c^2 \cdot \rho_b = (4 \cdot h \cdot f_{p1})^2 \cdot \rho_b \quad (3)$$

218 where c is the velocity of the longitudinal elastic wave propagated through a powder bed, ρ_b is the bulk
219 density of a powder material, h is the powder bed height, and f_{p1} is the primary absorption peak
220 frequency.

221 The frequency dependencies of the normal incidence sound absorption coefficient α of the investigated
 222 loose powders in the frequency range of 250–6400 Hz were obtained using the transfer function
 223 method ISO 10534-2, which is based on the partial standing wave principle [31]. This method
 224 employed a BK 4206 two-microphone acoustic impedance tube in combination with a BK 3560-B-
 225 030 signal pulse multi-analyzer and a BK 2706 power amplifier (Brüel & Kjær, Nærum, Denmark).
 226 The normal incidence sound absorption coefficient α is then determined from the equations [32]:

$$227 \quad \alpha = 1 - |r|^2 = 1 - \left| \frac{H_{12} - H_I}{H_R - H_{12}} \cdot e^{-2j \cdot k_0 \cdot x_1} \right|^2 \quad (4)$$

$$228 \quad H_{12} = \frac{p_2}{p_1} = \frac{e^{j \cdot k_0 \cdot x_2} + r \cdot e^{-j \cdot k_0 \cdot x_2}}{e^{j \cdot k_0 \cdot x_1} + r \cdot e^{-j \cdot k_0 \cdot x_1}} \quad (5)$$

$$229 \quad H_I = e^{-j \cdot k_0 \cdot (x_1 - x_2)} \quad (6)$$

$$230 \quad H_R = e^{j \cdot k_0 \cdot (x_1 - x_2)} \quad (7)$$

231 where r is the normal incidence reflection factor, H_{12} is the complex acoustic transfer function, H_I is
 232 the transfer function for the incident wave, H_R is the transfer function for the reflected wave, j is the
 233 imaginary unit, k_0 is the wave number, x_1 and x_2 are the distances of the two microphone positions
 234 from the reference plane ($x = 0$), and p_1 and p_2 are the complex acoustic pressures at two microphone
 235 positions. The sound absorption properties of the studied loose powder beds were investigated using
 236 an acoustic impedance tube with an inside diameter of 29 mm, for various powder bed heights ranging
 237 from 5 to 80 mm. Experimental measurements of the normal incidence sound absorption coefficient
 238 were conducted at an ambient temperature of 21°C.

239 The stability of the prepared decorated CF materials was evaluated by testing the leachability of
 240 selected elements. Leachates were prepared by mixing CF with distilled water in a ratio of 1:20. For
 241 this purpose, CF were mixed with distilled water at a ratio of 1:20. A static test (S) was performed by
 242 placing the mixture in a beaker, while dynamic tests were conducted using a horizontal agitation (H)
 243 using shaker device and a rotational overhead agitation with Heidolph Reax 20 shaker (R). All tests
 244 were performed for 24h at room temperature. The CF were then removed by filtration and stabilised

245 with HNO₃ (analytical grade, 65 %). Ag, Si, Al, Ca, Fe, K, Mg and Ti were determined using atomic
 246 emission spectrometry with inductively coupled plasma (AES-ICP) Spectro Arcos (SPECTRO
 247 Analytical Instruments Inc., Germany).

248 4 Results and discussion

249 4.1 Characterization of functional properties

250 Cenospheres (CF) are primarily composed of SiO₂ (50–65 wt.%), Al₂O₃ (20–37 wt.%), and Fe₂O₃ (1–
 251 11 wt.%) [33]. Due to their high SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ content, they are often referred to as hollow ceramic
 252 aluminosilicate microspheres. The main elements expressed in oxide in raw CF are Al₂O₃ (27–31
 253 wt.%) and SiO₂ (57.9–60.1 wt.%), along with smaller quantities of other oxides such as CaO, Fe₂O₃,
 254 K₂O, MgO, P₂O₅, and TiO₂, are denoted in Table 1. The combined SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ content typically
 255 ranges from 85–92%.

256 Prior to acid treatment with piranha solution, all CF fractions contained 2–3 wt.% Fe₂O₃. The CF
 257 fractions sized 40–80 μm and 80–125 μm exhibited relatively high CaO levels at 5.74 and 3.68 wt.%,
 258 respectively. As shown in Table 1, the acid treatment caused only slight changes in the overall chemical
 259 composition of the CF. However, there was a noticeable reduction in the concentrations of Mg and Fe
 260 cations, which were removed during the acidification process. Other elements, including P, K, Ca, and
 261 Ti, also experienced reductions, even though to a lesser extent.

262 The leaching of major elements of CF chemical composition, Al and Si, was minimal, as evidenced
 263 by the stable quantity ratios of these elements before and after treatment. This suggests that the
 264 structural integrity of the aluminosilicate framework is largely preserved during the acid treatment.

265 **Table 1.** Chemical composition expressed in oxides of original cenospheres and after piranha solution for different
 266 fractions evaluated using XRF method, the highlighted elements are of most noticeable change.

	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	MgO	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃
	wt.%								
CF_4080	27.0	57.9	0.98	0.88	1.35	5.74	1.28	3.06	2.14
CF_4080_2PS	28.8	64.4	0.75	0.36	1.41	0.81	1.21	1.98	2.24
CF_80125	29.2	58.7	0.79	0.72	1.18	3.68	1.40	2.55	2.01
CF_80125_2PS	31.1	62.1	0.89	0	1.28	0.85	1.23	1.99	2.00
CF_125160	31.7	60.1	0.96	0.35	1.13	1.15	1.39	2.26	1.90
CF_125160_2PS	32.5	61.3	0.67	0	1.08	0.82	1.43	1.73	1.90

CF_160200	31.8	58.0	0.85	0.54	1.03	1.57	1.30	2.19	1.82
CF_160200_2PS	33.3	60.0	0.90	0.23	1.11	0.89	1.25	1.98	1.80

267

268 The ratio $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is a geochemical indicator of the mineral coal forms, from which the cenospheres
 269 are formed [33]. This $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio is close to 2 wt.% and showed a slight decrease when the CF
 270 size is bigger. The aluminosilicate composition of the original and acid treated CF size fractions can
 271 be described by the general regression equations $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 3.74 - 0.06 [\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3]$ and $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 =$
 272 $4.98 - 0.1 [\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3]$, respectively (Figure 1).

273

274 **Fig. 1** Dependences of the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio on the Al_2O_3 content.

274

275 After decoration of Ag nanoparticles on the surface of CF, the silver content (determined by XRF
 276 analysis) was follows: 5.82 wt.% in sample CF4080_2PS_Ag; 6.12 wt.% in CF80125_2PS_Ag; 7.14
 277 wt.% in CF125160_2PS_Ag and 6.92 wt.% in CF160200_2PS_Ag.

278 Figure 2 shows the evaluated phase composition of cenospheres: raw, acid treated and after Ag
 279 modification. In the XRD patterns of raw CF were identified as major crystalline phases mullite (M;
 280 $3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$; PDF card No. 01-089-2645) and quartz (Q; SiO_2 ; PDF card No. 01-085-0797).
 281 Moreover, the reflections of calcite (C; CaCO_3 ; PDF card No. 01-086-2334) were observed in raw CF

282 in the finest fractions (40 – 80 μm and 80-125 μm). A considerable amount of amorphous material was
 283 observed in XRD patterns as wide band in the 2θ range between 15 – 30° for all CF samples.
 284 Comparison of the XRD patterns of the original CF and those after etching reveals that the phase
 285 composition of the CF was largely unaffected by the chemical etching process. The mullite and quartz
 286 phases persisted in the CF after acid treatment, owing to their low reactivity [29]. Notably, a new
 287 reflection appeared following the acid treatment and subsequent Ag modification, indicating the
 288 formation of a new phase. The XRD patterns of CF modified with Ag indicate the presence of mullite,
 289 quartz and moreover face-centered cubic Ag crystals (S; PDF card No. 01-071-6549) and chlorargyrite
 290 (Ch; AgCl; PDF card No. 00-006-0480).

291

292 **Fig. 2** XRD patterns of cenospheres samples arranged with relation to size fractions: a) 40-80 μm , b) 80-125 μm , c) 125-
 293 160 μm , d) 160-200 μm .

294 The FTIR spectra show bands characteristic for cenospheres, see Fig. 3 (see also Figure in
 295 attachment). The bands observed at approximately 435 cm^{-1} and 540 cm^{-1} are associated with the
 296 vibrations of O-Si-O silicate tetrahedra [34]. Additionally, the stretching vibration of the Si-O-Si
 297 bridge in quartz, present in fly ash, is evident at 800 cm^{-1} [35]. The presence of mullite was confirmed
 298 by a band at $\sim 916 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, corresponding to aluminum in the octahedral position. However, this band
 299 was absent in the smallest CF fraction (40–80 μm) [36].

300
 301 **Fig. 3** FTIR spectra of cenospheres samples arranged with relation to size fractions: a) CF 40-80 μm , b) CF 80-125 μm ,
 302 c) CF 125-160 μm , d) CF 160-200 μm (black lines – pure CF; red lines – CF after PS solution, blue lines – CF after PS
 303 and with Ag nanoparticles).

304 The SiO_4 vibration is presented by asymmetric in-plane stretching vibration of Si-O tetrahedra at
305 $\sim 1032 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Si-O(Si) and 1087 cm^{-1} , respectively except the CF 160-200 sample. In this sample
306 the most intensive band is shifted to 1045 cm^{-1} which indicate the gradually increasing amount of
307 quartz in the samples (from CF 40-80 to CF 160-200) with the largest portion of quartz in CF160-200,
308 this phenomenon was described by Mozgawa et al. [35]. The following bands at 874 and 1434 cm^{-1}
309 relate to calcite. The formation of CaCO_3 is done by reaction of calcium hydroxide with atmospheric
310 CO_2 - the possible formation of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and then CaCO_3 is due to significant amount of CaO present
311 in the sample (see XRF analysis) [35, 37]. The amount of calcite decreases with increasing size CF
312 fraction, which is visible at the last fraction CF 160-200, where no calcite bands are detected. The last
313 two bands at 1627 cm^{-1} and $\sim 3390 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ arises from OH vibration of adsorbed water [38]. Acid etching
314 of CF leads to removal of calcite (874 cm^{-1} and 1434 cm^{-1}). The OH bands of water (around 3390 cm^{-1}
315 $^{-1}$) were also decreased. The most intensive band is shifted to higher value from 1032 to 1036 cm^{-1} (in
316 the case of samples CF 40-80 and CF 80-125) and from $1036/1045 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to 1061 cm^{-1} (in the case of
317 samples CF 125-160 and CF 160-200). The addition of green synthesized Ag nanoparticles into the
318 CF leads to presence of some organic bands in FTIR spectrum, e.g., the band at 3388 cm^{-1} corresponds
319 to O-H functional hydroxyl groups.

320 **4.3 Morphology of cenospheres and silver nanoparticles distribution**

321 Figure 4 shows electron microscope images of all prepared CF fractions – input (A-D), purified with
322 pirhana solution (F-H) and mixed with nanosilver (I-L). The differences between the size fractions are
323 obvious, as well as the effect of purification and etching with a mixture of sulfuric acid and hydrogen
324 peroxide, after which the surface of the CF was more exposed and the internal structures were also
325 revealed. At applied magnification, silver nanoparticles cannot be observed, however, the effect of
326 stabilizing organic phyto-components caused a slight charging of the CF during the observation in the
327 microscope chamber.

328 **Fig. 4** Electron images document the morphology and size of the CF – input samples (A-D); etched in pirhana solution (E-
 329 H); mixed with bioreduced silver nanoparticles (I-L) for all prepared size fractions – 40-80 μm (A, E, I); 80-125 μm (B, F,
 330 J); 125-160 μm (C, G, K) and 160-200 μm (D, H, L); scale 50 μm.

331 The silver nanoparticles are polydisperse with an average size of 45 nm (Fig. 5a, scale 100 nm). To
 332 better visualize the silver nanoparticles distributed on the surface of CF, material contrast in the
 333 backscattered electron mode (COMPO) was used. It is evident from the electron images that nanosilver
 334 does not decorate the CF evenly, but rather accumulates in places of structural defects (Fig. 5b, scale
 335 10 μm), or leaves a ring after drying the sample (Fig. 5c, scale 10 μm). Nanoparticles occur on the
 336 surface of the CF individually, as larger agglomerated formations (Fig. 5d, scale 100 nm) or in thicker
 337 layers (Fig. 5e, scale 10 μm). They are occasionally found free outside the CF. These silver

338 nanoparticles will probably release more easily into the surrounding solution during stability leaching
339 tests (Fig. 5f, scale 1 μm). The images demonstrate distinct, irregular crystallization patterns forming
340 a dense network of crystallites—small, ordered regions with sharply defined grain boundaries. These
341 crystallites appear as closely packed, polygonal forms, creating a compact, granular structure.

342 **Fig. 5** Size and morphology of silver nanoparticles prepared via bioreduction with Verbena plant extract (5A, scale 100
343 nm, STEM regime); silver-based nanoparticles decorate the surface of CF-fragments after PS treatment (5B-F).
344 In the EDS map sum spectrum of CF decorated with nanosilver (Fig. 6), the main elements from the
345 CF composition were identified as Al (8.3 wt.%), Si (6.3 wt.%) and O (51.7 wt.%). The contribution
346 to the total Al content is attributed to the sample holder and Cu (1.3 wt.%) from the used Cu-grid for
347 STEM observation of silver nanoparticles. Gold was used to increase the conductivity of the sample
348 for better observation in the electron microscope chamber. Along with silver (0.5 wt.%), Cl (0.1 wt.%),
349 which is often an anthropogenic impurity in plant precursors, and C from organic material of plant
350 origin (31.6 wt.%) can also be identified. Accompanying elements in the CF composition can also be
351 Fe and Ti (both 0.1 wt.%). Chemical elements with low molecular weight such as C and O are
352 quantitatively overestimated in the EDS analysis, which is evidenced by the higher standard deviation.
353

Fig. 6 Nanocrystalline silver layer deposited on the surface of the cenosphere with silver EDS map and summary EDS spectrum.

The results of true density measurements, obtained using He pycnometry, are summarized in Table 2. These findings reveal a consistent increase in density for all cenosphere fractions after modification. The incorporation of silver nanoparticles led to the most significant increase, with density values more than doubling for the 40–80 μm and 80–125 μm fractions compared to the original samples. Curiously the smallest and largest particle size fractions are showing similar values, however this phenomenon is caused by relatively similar porosity of large spherical particles (holes in the spheres and space around) and space around the fraction of the spheres and small spheres.

Table 2. True density measurement results of CF samples.

Sample	Density, g/cm ³
CF_4080	1.0224
CF_4080_2PS	1.1420
CF_4080_2PS_Ag	1.4391
CF_80125	0.6118
CF_80125_2PS	1.0314
CF_80125_2PS_Ag	1.4300
CF_125160	0.7523
CF_125160_2PS	1.1463
CF_125160_2PSAg	1.4664
CF_160200	1.0572
CF_160_200_2PS	1.1800
CF_160200_2PS_Ag	1.5710

366

367 4.3 Sound absorption measurements

368 In general, sound absorption properties of loose powders are influenced by different factors, such as
369 their density, particles' shape and size, porosity, thickness of the studied material layer and
370 compressibility.

371 The effect of the particle size on the frequency dependencies of the sound absorption coefficient of the
372 investigated unconsolidated loose powders of a given powder bed height is depicted in Fig. 7. The
373 noise reduction coefficient (NRC) and the mean sound absorption coefficient (α_m) were subsequently
374 evaluated based on these frequency dependencies.

375

376 **Fig. 7** Frequency dependencies of the sound absorption coefficient: a) for raw CF powders with a bed height of 10 mm, b)
377 for modified Ag CF powders with a bed height of 25 mm.

378 The results of these coefficients depending on the powder height (h) for the studied CF powders are
379 presented in Tables 3 and 4. It was found based on these results that the particle size had a significant
380 effect on NRC and α_m for the raw CF powders as shown in Table 3. It can be concluded that the sound
381 absorption properties (i.e., the coefficients NRC and α_m) generally increased with increasing the
382 particle size of the investigated raw CF. This phenomenon is mainly related to the porosity of powder
383 materials.

384

385
386

Table 3. Results of the calculated and measured acoustical and mechanical quantities of studied raw CF powders at selected powder bed height h .

Sample	Quantity	h (mm)						
		5	10	15	25	30	50	80
CF_4080	fp_1 (Hz)	2520	1400	1168	736	704	664	552
	NRC (-)	0.084	0.088	0.121	0.136	0.106	0.103	0.146
	α_m (-)	0.203	0.218	0.212	0.219	0.202	0.199	0.226
	c (m/s)	50.4	56.0	70.1	73.6	84.5	132.8	176.6
	K (MPa)	2.60	3.21	5.02	5.54	7.30	18.03	31.90
CF_80125	fp_1 (Hz)	3080	1608	1176	816	784	736	664
	NRC (-)	0.066	0.130	0.127	0.158	0.155	0.131	0.108
	α_m (-)	0.217	0.233	0.223	0.220	0.223	0.230	0.228
	c (m/s)	61.6	64.3	70.6	81.6	94.1	147.2	212.5
	K (MPa)	2.32	2.53	3.05	4.07	5.42	13.26	27.62
CF_125160	fp_1 (Hz)	3344	1936	1456	1000	952	832	832
	NRC (-)	0.084	0.171	0.129	0.182	0.166	0.136	0.129
	α_m (-)	0.259	0.258	0.252	0.265	0.250	0.257	0.244
	c (m/s)	66.9	77.4	87.4	100.0	114.2	166.4	266.2
	K (MPa)	3.36	4.51	5.74	7.52	9.82	20.83	53.33
CF_160200	fp_1 (Hz)	4752	1976	1632	1096	920	904	872
	NRC (-)	0.086	0.180	0.182	0.193	0.205	0.194	0.210
	α_m (-)	0.291	0.319	0.319	0.320	0.336	0.313	0.351
	c (m/s)	95.0	79.0	97.9	109.6	110.4	180.8	279.0
	K (MPa)	9.55	6.60	10.14	12.70	12.89	34.56	82.32

387
388

Table 4. Results of the calculated and measured acoustical and mechanical quantities of studied modified Ag CF powders at selected powder bed heights h .

Sample	Quantity	h (mm)						
		5	10	15	25	30	50	80
CF_4080_2PS_Ag	fp_1 (Hz)	2312	1360	1012	712	696	580	560
	NRC (-)	0.116	0.120	0.151	0.132	0.104	0.110	0.143
	α_m (-)	0.226	0.229	0.248	0.248	0.228	0.217	0.247
	c (m/s)	46.2	54.4	60.7	71.2	83.5	116.0	177.3
	K (MPa)	3.08	4.26	5.31	7.30	10.04	19.36	45.23
CF_80125_2PS_Ag	fp_1 (Hz)	2216	1376	936	656	656	552	554
	NRC (-)	0.131	0.096	0.147	0.129	0.132	0.182	0.159
	α_m (-)	0.253	0.225	0.260	0.270	0.262	0.287	0.291
	c (m/s)	44.3	55.0	56.2	65.6	78.7	110.4	177.3
	K (MPa)	2.81	4.33	4.51	6.15	8.86	17.43	44.94
CF_125160_2PS_Ag	fp_1 (Hz)	2656	1384	1032	744	696	632	600
	NRC (-)	0.075	0.127	0.160	0.145	0.142	0.135	0.151
	α_m (-)	0.233	0.265	0.262	0.269	0.278	0.251	0.283
	c (m/s)	53.1	55.4	61.9	74.4	83.5	126.4	192.0
	K (MPa)	4.14	4.49	5.62	8.12	10.23	23.43	54.06
CF_160200_2PS_Ag	fp_1 (Hz)	2496	1504	1144	824	752	672	632
	NRC (-)	0.096	0.120	0.151	0.154	0.148	0.151	0.158
	α_m (-)	0.254	0.232	0.269	0.254	0.266	0.280	0.279
	c (m/s)	49.9	60.2	68.6	82.4	90.2	134.4	202.2
	K (MPa)	3.91	5.69	7.40	10.67	12.79	28.38	64.26

389

390 As a result, sound waves are more likely to be reflected between particles, which increases the
 391 conversion of acoustic energy into heat and increases the sound absorption of powder materials with
 392 larger particle sizes. Different sound absorption properties were observed after the addition of Ag
 393 nanoparticles to the raw CF powders. Again, the lowest values of NRC and α_m coefficients were found
 394 for the modified Ag CF powders with particle sizes in the range of 40-80 μm . For other particle sizes,
 395 the sound absorption behaviour of the modified Ag CF powders was very similar, so that the effect of
 396 particle size on the NRC and α_m coefficients was negligible, as shown in Table 4.

397 The effect of powder bed height h on the sound absorption properties of two types of loose CF powders
 398 is shown in Fig. 8. It is evident that powder bed height had a significant influence on the primary
 399 absorption peak frequency (f_{p1}), which generally decreased as the powder bed height increased, as
 400 shown in Tables 3 and 4. However, the powder bed height of the unconsolidated CF powders had a
 401 negligible influence on their overall sound absorption properties.

402
 403 **Fig. 8** Frequency dependencies of the sound absorption coefficient for different loose powder beds heights: a) for raw CF
 404 powders with fractions of 80-125 μm , b) for modified Ag CF powders with fractions of 160-200 μm .

405 It was found based on the calculated α_m values (see Tables 3 and 4) that raw CF powders with particle
 406 sizes in the range of 160–200 μm exhibited a higher ability to absorb sound compared to the modified
 407 Ag CF powders across almost the entire range of powder bed heights. Conversely, the modified Ag

408 CF powders with smaller particle sizes (i.e., from 40 to 125 μm) demonstrated better sound absorption
409 properties than the raw CF powders over a substantial range of powder bed heights.

410 Finally, the experimentally measured frequency dependencies of the sound absorption coefficient α
411 were used to determine the velocity (c) of the longitudinal elastic wave propagating through the
412 powder bed and the longitudinal elasticity coefficient (K) of the investigated CF powders. These
413 quantities were calculated based on the obtained values of the primary absorption peak frequency f_{p1}
414 (see Figs 7 and 8) and the bulk density (ρ_b) according to Equation (3). Their values for various powder
415 bed heights are given in Tables 3 and 4. As shown in Fig. 9, the longitudinal elasticity coefficient (K),
416 and thus the mechanical stiffness of the CF powders, generally increased with powder bed height.
417 Higher mechanical stiffness was observed for both raw CF and modified Ag CF powders containing
418 the largest particles (i.e., from 160 to 200 μm). Conversely, the lowest mechanical stiffness was found
419 in both types of CF powders with particle sizes ranging from 80 to 125 μm . From the comparison of
420 both types of the investigated loose powders (see Figs 9a and 9b), it is clear that higher mechanical
421 stiffness was generally found for the modified Ag CF powders. Only in the case of powders containing
422 the largest particle sizes (i.e., from 160 to 200 μm), the raw CF powders exhibited higher values of the
423 longitudinal elasticity coefficient, and thus higher mechanical stiffness, compared to the modified Ag
424 CF powders. The bulk modulus K , indicating material stiffness, shows a clear positive correlation with
425 density. High-density samples (e.g., CF_160200_2PS_Ag with 64.26 MPa) generally exhibited
426 significantly higher mechanical stiffness compared to low-density ones (e.g., CF_80125 with 27.62
427 MPa).

428

429 **Fig. 9** Effect of the loose powder bed height on the longitudinal elastic coefficient: a) for raw CF powders with different
 430 fractions, b) for modified Ag CF powders with different fractions.

431 Higher density materials (e.g., CF_160200_2PS_Ag with 1.571 g/cm³) are generally characterized
 432 by higher *NRC* values, indicating better sound absorption. Lower density materials (e.g., CF_80125
 433 with 0.6118 g/cm³) exhibited lower *NRC* values, suggesting less efficient sound absorption. The
 434 average speed of sound (see Fig. 10) was generally higher in denser samples (e.g.,
 435 CF_160200_2PS_Ag with 101.6 m/s) compared to lower-density ones (e.g., CF_80125_2PS_Ag with
 436 87.1 m/s). Dense materials tend to be stiffer, which accelerates sound wave propagation. It can also be
 437 concluded that the decoration of the CF with Ag resulted in a reduction in the speed of sound, as shown
 438 in Fig. 10.

439

440

Fig. 10 Comparison of average values of sounds speed vs true density of all samples.

441

442 **4. 4 Stability testing of decorated CF**

443 One of the main goals was both the preparation of a functional material with the required properties
444 and its stability in the environment in which it will be applied. Therefore, the leachability test under
445 static and dynamic conditions was used to determine the stability of decorated CF materials.

446 The percentage of Ag released from CF_4080_2PS_Ag, CF_125160_2PS_Ag and
447 CF_160200_2PS_Ag samples to the leachates after the static (S) leaching test were comparable (see
448 Fig. 11). A slightly higher amount of Ag was released from CF_80125_2PS_Ag, which also
449 corresponds with higher amounts of released Al, Fe, and Mg compared to other CF samples (Table 5).
450 This could be due to the lowest density of CF_80125 (1.43 g/cm³) compared to the other CF Ag
451 decorated samples (see Table 3) as the distilled water probably affected the surface and pores more
452 intensively.

453 The leaching test under dynamic conditions (D) did not significantly affect the release of Ag from
454 sample CF_4080_2PS_Ag compared to CF_80125_2PS_Ag, CF_125160_2PS_Ag and
455 CF_160200_2PS_Ag where the Ag concentrations released under dynamic conditions were higher.
456 The amount of Ag released from CF_80125_2PS_Ag, CF_125160_2PS_Ag and CF_160200_2PS_Ag
457 samples in the dynamic (D) leaching test were not significantly different. Compared to the previous
458 static (S) test, the dynamic leaching test also had no significant effect on the release of the monitored
459 elements from the CF materials.

460 The dependence was observed after the rotation (R) leaching test. The proportion of Ag released into
461 the leachates obtained by rotation test (R) increased with increasing fraction size. Even when dynamic
462 conditions were used during the leachability test, there was no significant release of Ag from the CF
463 samples tested. Even in the rotation leaching test, the monitored elements did not loosen significantly
464 more than in the previous S and D tests.

465 In general, the highest amounts of released alkaline elements (Ca, K and Mg) were determined in the
 466 leachates (S, D and R) obtained from the material with the lowest size fraction CF_4080_2PS_Ag than
 467 from the CF_80125_2PS_Ag, CF_125160_2PS_Ag and CF_160200_2PS_Ag. This may be related to
 468 the small particle size and the relative ease of release of these elements into the aqueous environment.
 469 While Al and Fe are mainly released from materials with a larger fraction of particle size (Table 5).

470

471 **Fig. 11** The percentage of Ag leached from CF_4080_2PS_Ag, CF_80125_2PS_Ag, CF_125160_2PS_Ag and
 472 CF_160200_2PS_Ag under static (S), dynamic (D) and rotation (R) conditions.

473 **Table 5** The amount (in wt.%) of selected elements released from CF samples after static (S), dynamic (D) and rotational
 474 (R) leaching tests.

	Ag (wt.%)	Al (wt.%)	Ca (wt.%)	Fe (wt.%)	K (wt.%)	Mg (wt.%)	Si (wt.%)
S_CF_4080		0.003	0.344	0.002	0.010	0.030	0.012
S_CF_4080_2PS_Ag	0.006	0.002	0.310	0.001	0.017	0.030	0.008
S_CF_80125_2PS_Ag	0.009	0.012	0.016	0.003	0.012	0.007	0.005
S_CF_125160_2PS_Ag	0.008	0.008	0.007	0.001	0.007	0.003	0.002
S_CF_160200_2PS_Ag	0.007	0.009	0.009	0.001	0.008	0.004	0.010
D_CF_40_80		0.002	0.332	<0.500	0.010	0.029	0.012
D_CF_4080_2PS_Ag	0.001	0.002	0.302	<0.500	0.016	0.028	0.008
D_CF_80125_2PS_Ag	0.008	0.011	0.015	0.002	0.008	0.006	0.005
D_CF_125160_2PS_Ag	0.010	0.008	0.017	0.002	0.007	0.006	0.004
D_CF_160200_2PS_Ag	0.008	0.009	0.016	0.002	0.015	0.003	0.003
R_CF_40_80		0.001	0.366	<0.500	0.007	0.028	0.013
R_CF_4080_2PS_Ag	0.001	0.001	0.358	<0.500	0.021	0.032	0.009
R_CF_80125_2PS_Ag	0.002	0.010	0.021	0.002	0.015	0.004	0.002
R_CF_125160_2PS_Ag	0.006	0.010	0.016	0.003	0.014	0.006	0.011
R_CF_160200_2PS_Ag	0.010	0.008	0.009	0.001	0.008	0.003	0.003

475

476 It can be concluded that Ag is firmly attached to the CF surface, selected elements have not been
477 released significantly and, therefore, the CF materials can be considered stable under the stated
478 conditions.

479

480 **5 Conclusions**

481 Studied cenosphere powder samples were compared for all possible combined effects of stability and
482 materials characteristics. The static stability test provides a controlled, predictable environment
483 suitable for analyzing the stability and equilibrium behavior of sorbent materials. The dynamic stability
484 test offers insights into the performance under agitation or movement, emphasizing mobilization and
485 release rates. For larger fractions, greater silver release was observed under rotational conditions,
486 which may suggest less stability of these samples under dynamic conditions. Each process affects the
487 stability of the samples in solution differently, which may be important when choosing the appropriate
488 method to test the stability of materials in different environments. However, after stability tests, silver
489 nanoparticles remain on the cenospheres. Despite this, studies indicate good stability of cenospheres
490 under static conditions, suggesting that modified cenospheres may be effective in long-term
491 environmental clean-up applications without excessive release of silver into water. Thanks to the
492 modification of cenospheres with silver nanoparticles, a cover of organic compounds remains, which
493 in the future may provide also a catalytic effect and exhibit electrical properties. This study also
494 presented a non-destructive sound absorption test to evaluate both the sound absorption properties and
495 mechanical stiffness of bulk powders. The results indicate that CF samples with larger particle sizes
496 exhibited a higher ability to absorb sound. The mechanical stiffness of the studied CF, characterized
497 by the bulk modulus, significantly increased with powder bed height and density. For these reasons,
498 the highest sound absorption ($\alpha_{max} = 0.351$) and mechanical stiffness ($K_{max} = 82.32$ MPa) were
499 obtained for the CF_160200 sample with the maximum powder bed height ($h_{max} = 80$ mm).
500 Additionally, CF decorated with silver nanoparticles generally exhibited higher mechanical stiffness

501 compared to raw CF. In summary, the study demonstrates that silver-modified cenospheres exhibit
502 favorable structural stability, limited silver leaching under various environmental conditions, and
503 enhanced functional properties. Their improved sound absorption performance, increased mechanical
504 stiffness, and potential catalytic activity make them promising candidates for applications in
505 environmental remediation, acoustic insulation, and multifunctional composite materials.

506

507 **Availability of data and materials**

508 The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in repository ZENODO at
509 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14272437> [39].

510 **Competing interests**

511 The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

512 **Author contributions**

513 Conceptualization: GSM, GK, Methodology: MA, JK, GK, GSM, Software: MA, JK, LK, MT,
514 Validation: GSM, JK, MA, Formal analysis: MA, JK, GK, LK, MV, MT, Investigation: MA, JK, GK,
515 LK, MV, JM, MT, Resources: MA, JK, GK, Data curation: MA, JK, GK, Writing-original draft: MA,
516 JK, MV, Writing-review&editing: GSM, MA, JK, GK, Visualization: MA, JK, GK, LK, Supervision:
517 GSM, Project administration: GSM, GK, Funding acquisition: GSM

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524

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